

Survey of Video Game Bugs

* Required

1. Name *

2. Organization *

3. Job Title *

4. Name the game you play most often *

5. Which of the following is your area of expertise? *

Select all that apply.

Check all that apply.

Game Development

Game Testing

Game Play

6. How long have you been playing video games? (in years) *

Only enter numbers greater than equal to 0.

7. How long have you been developing video games? (in years) *

Only enter numbers greater than equal to 0.

8. How long have you been testing video games? (in years) *

Only enter numbers greater than equal to 0.

9. What genre of video games do you play? *

Select all that apply.

Check all that apply.

- Action e.g. Tekken
- Role Playing Games (RPG) e.g. Final Fantasy IV
- Platform e.g. Super Mario
- Racing e.g. Asphalt 8: Airborne
- Rythm e.g. Dance Dance Revolution
- Shooter e.g. Sniper 3D
- Casual e.g. Angry Birds
- Board e.g. Monopoly
- 3-match e.g. Candy Crush
- Multiplayer online battle arena (MOBA) e.g. DOTA 2

Other: _____

Important Descriptions

We used Likert scales to gauge the FREQUENCY, SEVERITY, and PRIORITY of our identified video game bug categories, as follows:

Frequency

5-point Likert scale for frequency of video game bugs as follows:

1. Always: represents the faults that are generally encountered in all games.
2. Often: represents the faults that generally occur more than 7 out of 10 times.
3. Sometimes: represents the faults that generally occur more than 5-7 out of 10 times.
4. Rarely: represents the faults that generally occur more than 1-4 out of 10 times.
5. Never: represents frequency of faults that according to the practitioner do not occur.

Severity

6-point Likert scale for severity is used in the survey questionnaire for video game bugs as follows:

1. **Blocker:** Such an error makes it impossible to proceed with using or testing the software. For instance, it shuts an application down.
2. **Critical:** It is an incorrect functioning of a particular area of business-critical software functionality, like unsuccessful installation or failure of its main features.
3. **Major:** An error has a significant impact on an application, but other inputs and parts of the system remain functional, so its use is still possible.
4. **Minor:** A defect is confusing or causes undesirable behavior but does not affect user experience significantly. Many UI bugs belong here.
5. **Low:** A bug that does not affect the functionality or is not obviously evident. It can be a problem with third-party apps, grammar, or spelling mistakes, etc.
6. **None:** represents severity of faults that according to the practitioner do not occur

Priority

6-point Likert scale for priority that should be allocated to fixing a certain type of bug in video game, as follows:

1. **Immediate:** represents the highest priority, to be given to the most critical game breaking bugs that should be fixed immediately.
2. **High:** represents the priority, to be given to the critical bugs.
3. **Medium:** represents the priority, to be given to the video game bugs that impact the game play but do not break the core game functionality.
4. **Low:** represents the priority, to be given to the video game bugs that have very little impact to the game play experience.
5. **Trivial:** represents the lowest priority, to be given to the video game bugs that should be addressed eventually. Such an issue is not relevant to core functions rather it relates only to the attractiveness or pleasantness of the system.
6. **None:** represents priority of faults that according to the practitioner do not occur.

Gaming Balance

A balanced game is one in which players that have equivalent or similar skill sets have an equal chance of winning. This category specifically refers to the unbalanced gameplay.

Too Easy: Players find it too easy to play a game. It is especially critical if a particular set of parameters allows for unfair advantages in multiplayer games. In Hearthstone if a player plays "jerry rig carpenter", it reduces the mana value needed to play cards to zero which is equivalent to handing a free win

Too Hard: Players find it too difficult to finish the game. This includes difficulty in finishing a task due to obscure design. In Fallout Tactics, there are some missions where the whole map depends on finding one key in an obscure place.

Unwinnable: Players are unable to finish the game especially if it is due to an overly competent AI or convoluted game logic or game constraints such as small timers or impossible to obtain in-game items. In the Political Machine, the AI was too competent. When player got up to George Washington to play. The opponent AI won every state.

10. What type of Gaming Balance issues have you encountered while playing video games? *

Select all that apply.

Check all that apply.

Too Easy

Too Hard

Unwinnable

Other: _____

11. Which of the Gaming Balance sub-categories do you find unnecessary? *

Select all that apply.

Check all that apply.

Too Easy

Too Hard

Unwinnable

None

No Opinion

12. Provide reason(s) if you have selected any unnecessary category for previous question.

13. How often do you encounter Gaming Balance issues while playing video games? *

Mark only one oval.

- Always
- Often
- Sometimes
- Rarely
- Never

14. How would you rate severity of Gaming Balance issues while playing video games? *

Mark only one oval.

- Blocker
- Critical
- Major
- Minor
- Low
- None

15. How would you prioritize the need to fix Gaming Balance Issues encountered while playing video games? *

Mark only one oval.

- Immediate
- High
- Medium
- Low
- Trivial
- None

Implementation
Response
Faults

and Unresponsive Action.

Game Freeze: Game stops responding to any user action making progress impossible. In Majora's Mask, the game freezes when the player pushes the open icon button that appears on an underwater chest in Termina Field

Unresponsive Action: Player performs an in-game action successfully but the consequence or result of that action does not appear. In Cyberpunk 2077, when Takemura calls, the player takes the call but the NPC does not go away on end call.

Incorrect Reward/Punishment: An in-game action results in less or more reward compared to expected conversely less or more punishment than expected is also possible. In Super Mario Bros. Deluxe for Game Boy Color, if a player earns the Yoshi Medal at the same time as the Red Coins or High Score medals in Challenge mode, the player only receives the Yoshi medal, and the others are lost forever.

Incorrect Response Fault: Player performs an in-game action successfully but the consequence or result of that action is incorrect. Final Fantasy V had a weapon (the Chicken Knife), that would sometimes make the player run away from battle instead of doing an attack

16. What type of Implementation Response Issues have you encountered while playing video games? *

Select all that apply.

Check all that apply.

- Faulty Collision Detection
- Game Freeze
- Incorrect Response
- Incorrect Reward/Punishment
- Unresponsive action

Other: _____

17. Which of the Implementation Response sub-categories do you find unnecessary? *

Select all that apply.

Check all that apply.

- Faulty Collision Detection
- Game Freeze
- Incorrect Response
- Incorrect Reward/Punishment
- Unresponsive action
- None
- No Opinion

18. Provide reason(s) if you have selected any unnecessary category for previous question.

19. How often do you encounter Implementation Response issues while playing video games? *

Mark only one oval.

- Always
- Often
- Sometimes
- Rarely
- Never

20. How would you rate severity of Implementation Response issues while playing video games? *

Mark only one oval.

- Blocker
- Critical
- Major
- Minor
- Low
- None

21. How would you prioritize the need to fix Implementation Response Issues encountered while playing video games? *

Mark only one oval.

- Immediate
- High
- Medium
- Low
- Trivial
- None

Network faults

This category encompasses problems that arise due to a host game application's connection and communication with the game server as well as stable performance of game server during increased or unexpected network traffic.

Network Lag: Game play experience is impacted by lagging response in network games due to network speed constraints and Packet size constraints. In Fireteam, lag would result in the players shots missing, by the time the shot has been fired the intended target has gone around a corner

Synchronization: Different game states are visible to different players in a multi-player game. A game event starts according to an incorrect or different time zone. In Sins of a Solar Empire: Rebellion, partway through a match, players would find inconsistencies between the game states for different players

Connection Fault: Player is unable to connect with the game server. In Fallout 76, if multiple mannequins were dressed in same outfit it resulted in the players being logged out and unable to establish a connection again.

Network Overload: Game play experience of player is negatively impacted once number of connected players exceeds a specified amount. Wireless Pets could not even handle 10,000 users playing it simultaneously.

Packet Loss: A variety of packet loss or corruption problems that happen between game servers and client applications due to unreliable or unsustainable connection especially required for MMORPGs or MOBAs. In Toontown, a variety of packet loss problems were encountered.

22. What type of Network faults have you encountered while playing video games? *

Select all that apply.

Check all that apply.

- Connection Fault
- Network Lag
- Network Overload
- Packet Loss
- Synchronization

Other: _____

23. Which of the Network faults sub-categories do you find unnecessary? *

Select all that apply.

Check all that apply.

- Connection Fault
- Network Lag
- Network Overload
- Packet Loss
- Synchronization
- None
- No Opinion

24. Provide reason(s) if you have selected any unnecessary category for previous question.

25. How often do you encounter Network related issues while playing video games? *

Mark only one oval.

- Always
- Often
- Sometimes
- Rarely
- Never

26. How would you rate severity of Network related issues while playing video games? *

Mark only one oval.

- Blocker
- Critical
- Major
- Minor
- Low
- None

27. How would you prioritize the need to fix Network Issues encountered while playing video games? *

Mark only one oval.

- Immediate
- High
- Medium
- Low
- Trivial
- None

Faulty in-game sounds including both game's soundtrack, background ambience which is not directly generated by or linked to game environment, and narrative commentary;

Sound Faults

as well as, game's sound effects, background ambience which is directly generated by the game environment or elements, and the dialogue which takes place between characters like pressing the acceleration button in a racing game leads to the sound effect of an accelerating car.

Incorrect Sound: The sound behind an animation is incorrect or does not match the circumstances. In Whacked, missing sound resources led to either sounds missing or wrong sounds being played behind animations

Corrupted Sound: The sound behind an animation is corrupted or warped. In Final Zone II, a buzzing sound would start after the intro cutscene and continue throughout the game.

Unsynchronized Sound: The sound behind an animation is not correctly synchronized especially critical for Rhythm games. In Portable Black Squares and Claziquai, Edition's music became unsynchronized.

Too Short Sound: The sound ends before the animation completes. In Whacked, the sound of pendulum swing cut of before the animation ended.

Run Away Sound: The sound continues even after the animation completes. In The Italian Job, due to lack of sound resources available, the engines sounds looped very badly.

28. What type of Sound Issues have you encountered while playing video games?

*

Select all that apply.

Check all that apply.

- Corrupted
- Incorrect
- Run Away
- Too short
- Unsynchronized

Other: _____

29. Which of the Sound Issues sub-categories do you find unnecessary? *

Select all that apply.

Check all that apply.

- Corrupted
- Incorrect
- Run Away
- Too short
- Unsynchronized
- None
- No Opinion

30. Provide reason(s) if you have selected any unnecessary category for previous question.

31. How often do you encounter Sound issues while playing video games? *

Mark only one oval.

- Always
- Often
- Sometimes
- Rarely
- Never

32. How would you rate severity of Sound related issues while playing video games? *

Mark only one oval.

- Blocker
- Critical
- Major
- Minor
- Low
- None

33. How would you prioritize the need to fix Sound Issues encountered while playing video games? *

Mark only one oval.

- Immediate
- High
- Medium
- Low
- Trivial
- None

Temporal Faults

This category includes those faults which require some knowledge of previous game state to accurately categorize. For example, in Super Mario, Mario jumps up to the right height and continues to hover in mid-air (5.6. Invalid position over time). At any single point in time Mario is at a valid height however, by analyzing the coordinates of Mario over multiple state, the fault can be identified.

Accelerated Response Fault: Consequence of an action is accelerated giving unfair advantage or disadvantage especially in real time games. In King's Quest IV, when Rosella is in the ogre's house and must reach the door before he catches her, the ogre travels across the screen in seconds.

Delayed Response Fault: There is an unexpected delay in response to an action or a scenario. It is especially critical in real-time games. In King's Quest IV, at some random intervals the response to Rosella and other characters would lag.

Invalid Position Overtime: An in-game element is in an invalid position or motion at particular point in time. In Super Mario, if Mario jumps up to the right height and continues to hover in mid-air. At any single point in time Mario is at a valid height however, by analyzing the coordinates of Mario over multiple state, the fault can be identified.

36. Provide reason(s) if you have selected any unnecessary category for previous question.

37. How often do you encounter Temporal Faults while playing video games? *

Mark only one oval.

- Always
- Often
- Sometimes
- Rarely
- Never

38. How would you rate severity of Temporal faults while playing video games? *

Mark only one oval.

- Blocker
- Critical
- Major
- Minor
- Low
- None

39. How would you prioritize the need to fix Temporal Issues encountered while playing video games? *

Mark only one oval.

- Immediate
- High
- Medium
- Low
- Trivial
- None

Unexpected Crashes

This type of fault causes the entire game application to crash and exit.

Crash During Demo:	Game crashes unexpectedly during demo or tutorial practice sequence animation.
Crash During Non-Play Moments:	Game crashes unexpectedly during game Non-Playable Moments like story sequences or saving waits.
Crash At Start Up :	Game crashes unexpectedly during game start up sequence.
Crash After Action:	Game crashes unexpectedly after an in-game action is executed.
Crash At Shutdown:	Game crashes unexpectedly during game shut down sequence.

40. What type of Unexpected Crash Issues have you encountered while playing video games? *

Select all that apply.

Check all that apply.

- Crash After Action
- Crash At Shutdown
- Crash At Start Up
- Crash During Demo
- Crash During Non-play momentts

Other: _____

41. Which of the Unexpected Crash sub-categories do you find unnecessary? *

Select all that apply.

Check all that apply.

- Crash After Action
- Crash At Shutdown
- Crash At Start Up
- Crash During Demo
- Crash During Non-play momentts
- None
- No Opinion

42. Provide reason(s) if you have selected any unnecessary category for previous question.

43. How often do you encounter Unexpected Crash issues while playing video games? *

Mark only one oval.

- Always
- Often
- Sometimes
- Rarely
- Never

44. How would you rate severity of Unexpected Crash while playing video games? *

Mark only one oval.

- Blocker
- Critical
- Major
- Minor
- Low
- None

45. How would you prioritize the need to fix Unexpected Crash Issues encountered while playing video games? *

Mark only one oval.

- Immediate
- High
- Medium
- Low
- Trivial
- None

Navigational Faults

It is a navigational fault when players are unable to navigate to a place where they should be able to reach or conversely, they are able to navigate to a location they should not be able to access.

Unreachable Locations: A player is unable to reach a location in game or a position on screen that should be accessible. In Rastan on the Commodore 64, on the second level, it is impossible to make a jump over a flaming pit over 2 ropes to continue with the game progression

Unexpected Paths: A player is able to reach a location in game or a position on screen that should be inaccessible. In Fallout 77, players were able to reach places and levels that were still being developed.

46. What type of Navigational Issues have you encountered while playing video games? *

Select all that apply.

Check all that apply.

Unreachable Locations

Unexpected Path

Other: _____

47. Which of the Navigational Issues sub-categories do you find unnecessary? *

Select all that apply.

Check all that apply.

Unreachable Locations

Unexpected Path

None

No Opinion

48. Provide reason(s) if you have selected any unnecessary category for previous question.

49. How often do you encounter Navigational issues while playing video games? *

Mark only one oval.

Always

Often

Sometimes

Rarely

Never

50. How would you rate severity of Navigational issues while playing video games? *

Mark only one oval.

- Blocker
- Critical
- Major
- Minor
- Low
- None

51. How would you prioritize the need to fix Navigational Issues encountered while playing video games? *

Mark only one oval.

- Immediate
- High
- Medium
- Low
- Trivial
- None

Non-
Temporal
Faults

This category includes those faults which can be found by inspecting the game state at any point in time. For example, in Super Mario, Mario jumps up to a height higher than should be permitted .

Invalid Position: An in-game element is in an invalid position. If Mario in Super Mario bros. jumps to an invalid height it is invalid position.

Invalid Graphical Representation: Graphical representation of game elements or frame is faulty.

Invalid Value Change: An in-game event results in an incorrect value change. The Mafia 2 health bug is a notorious example of this fault. It caused the player's health to continuously decrease without any reprieve or cause.

Artificial Stupidity: Game AI shows poor reasoning. In Tresspassers, Dinosaurs were governed by a set of emotions which theoretically should have prompted them to pick appropriate responses at any time. However, in practice they oscillated rapidly between many activities, sometimes even standing still, and twitching as they tried to decide what to do

Faulty Information: The information provided to the player is faulty

or missing. In case of multiplayer games, this can include information regarding statistics and movements of allied players needed to make strategic decisions.

Faulty Actions: The execution of an in-game action by a player is faulty either due to inability to take action or ability to take impermissible action. In The Legend of Zelda: The Wind Waker, there is a glitch where if a player jumps and attacks on the back of the chest in the Ghost Ship, the game will crash .

Player Stuck Fault: Player is unable to progress in the game either due to inability to move from location or inability to complete a critical task. In Guacamelee, the player could get locked in the fight arena.

52. What type of Non-Temporal Faults have you encountered while playing video games? *

Select all that apply.

Check all that apply.

- Artificial Stupidity
- Invalid Value Change
- Player Stuck Issue
- Faulty Action
- Faulty Information
- Invalid Graphical Representation
- Invalid Position

Other: _____

53. Which of the Non Temporal Faults sub-categories do you find unnecessary? *

Select all that apply.

Check all that apply.

- Artificial Stupidity
- Invalid Value Change
- Player Stuck Issue
- Faulty Action
- Faulty Information
- Invalid Graphical Representation
- Invalid Position
- None
- No Opinion

54. Provide reason(s) if you have selected any unnecessary category for previous question.

55. How often do you encounter Non-Temporal Faults while playing video games? *

Mark only one oval.

- Always
- Often
- Sometimes
- Rarely
- Never

56. How would you rate severity of Non temporal faults while playing video games? *

Mark only one oval.

- Blocker
- Critical
- Major
- Minor
- Low
- None

57. How would you prioritize the need to fix Non Temporal Faults encountered while playing video games? *

Mark only one oval.

- Immediate
- High
- Medium
- Low
- Trivial
- None

Faulty
Actions

This category includes the faulty execution of an in-game action by a player either due to inability to act when permissible or ability to take impermissible action.

Action When Not Allowed: Player can take an in-game action that should not be permissible.] League of Legends: Season 11 as a bug that allows players to one shot enemies using all types of weapons even those that do not permit this action.

Action Not Possible: Player is unable to take an in-game action that should be permissible. . In Sanitarium, Max (the character the player controls) would get stuck around corners and claim "Can't go that way", even when path was available.

Multiple Action Inconsistency: An in-game action only appears faulty after it is combined with another action. In The Legend of Zelda: The Wind Waker, there is a glitch where if a player jumps and attacks on the back of the chest in the Ghost Ship, the game will crash.

Repeated Action Inconsistency: An in-game action only appears faulty after it is taken repeatedly. Psychonauts had a quirk where a player became unable to use double jump in a level where it was needed to jump between flaming grates while the water level is rapidly rising.

58. What type of Action Faults have you encountered while playing video games? *

Select all that apply.

Check all that apply.

- Action Not Possible
- Action When Not Allowed
- Multiple Action Inconsistency
- Repeated Action Inconsistency

Other: _____

59. Which of the Faulty Actions sub-categories do you find unnecessary? *

Select all that apply.

Check all that apply.

- Action Not Possible
- Action When Not Allowed
- Multiple Action Inconsistency
- Repeated Action Inconsistency
- None
- No Opinion

60. Provide reason(s) if you have selected any unnecessary category for previous question.

61. How often do you encounter Action Faults while playing video games? *

Mark only one oval.

- Always
- Often
- Sometimes
- Rarely
- Never

62. How would you rate severity of Faulty Actions while playing video games? *

Mark only one oval.

- Blocker
- Critical
- Major
- Minor
- Low
- None

63. How would you prioritize the need to fix Action Faults encountered while playing video games? *

Mark only one oval.

- Immediate
- High
- Medium
- Low
- Trivial
- None

Invalid
Graphical
Representation

This occurs when game graphics are faulty. In other words, graphical representation of game elements is faulty either due to rendering or location of appearance. When Mario catches a fire flower, he transforms to Fire Mario. If graphical representation of Mario remains unchanged or becomes something else then it will fall into this category of faults.

Corrupted Frame: Corrupted frames are visible. Elder Scrolls V: Skyrim, had a number rendering problems that resulted in corrupted frames being made visible to the players

Slow Loading: Frame loading rate is too slow. Mighty No.9, fell victim to slow frame rate

Extra Game Asset: An in-game element that should not be displayed is visible. In Jak X: Combat Racing, has a fault known as "saving" glitch where the save icon hangs on the game, forcing the player to hard reset to get rid of it .

Missing Game Asset: An in-game element that should be displayed is not present. In Donkey Kong Country 2, if a player picks up the barrel as it breaks, then the avatar is seen carrying an invisible barrel.

Abnormal Text: Text appears at wrong location or is

incomprehensible or may cover a characters or other objects. In Pokémon Red, Blue, Green and Yellow, the text describing 'MISSINGNO' pokemon was often glitchy

Incorrect Visual State Transition: An in-game element transitions to an incorrect state. The animation for a jumping Mario in Super Mario Bros., is different to that of a swimming Mario. If swimming Mario animation is made visible when Mario is jumping then it would fall into this category.

64. What type of Invalid Graphical Representations have you encountered while playing video games? *

Select all that apply.

Check all that apply.

- Abnormal Text
- Corrupted Frame
- Extra Game Asset
- Incorrect Visual State Transition
- Missing Game Asset
- Slow Loading

Other: _____

65. Which of the Invalid Graphical Representations sub-categories do you find unnecessary? *

Select all that apply.

Check all that apply.

- Abnormal Text
- Corrupted Frame
- Extra Game Asset
- Incorrect Visual State Transition
- Missing Game Asset
- Slow Loading
- None
- No Opinion

66. Provide reason(s) if you have selected any unnecessary category for previous question.

67. How often do you encounter Invalid Graphical Representations while playing video games? *

Mark only one oval.

- Always
- Often
- Sometimes
- Rarely
- Never

68. How would you rate severity of Invalid Graphical Representations while playing video games? *

Mark only one oval.

- Blocker
- Critical
- Major
- Minor
- Low
- None

69. How would you prioritize the need to fix Invalid Graphical Representations encountered while playing video games? *

Mark only one oval.

- Immediate
- High
- Medium
- Low
- Trivial
- None

Final Remarks

70. What major faults/errors/failures have you encountered during gameplay in video games other than the ones already classified? *

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